

VR applications, new devices and museums: visitors's feedback and learning. A preliminary report

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Abstract

Between the 15th of September 2005 and the 15th of November 2005, an exhibit on virtual and Roman archaeology was organized in Rome inside the Trajan's Market Museum. The event, "Building Virtual Rome" ("Immaginare Roma Antica"), was a great opportunity to show, inside an ancient monument, and for the first time together, many different projects, applications and installations about VR and Cultural Heritage. The uniqueness of the event was at the same time an occasion both for visitors and organizers to live a new experience, and to face some problematic aspects due, mainly to the meeting of high technological projects (some of them still at research level), cultural contents and also archaeological "containers". During the exhibit we tried to observe visitors and make some interviews, aimed at understanding their expectations at the beginning, their experience during their visit and finally their satisfaction/ dissatisfaction, learning, feedback, and interaction level during and after the visit. The preliminary results of this analysis are showing that the embodiment and the diverse difficulties to use different devices and software depend on many factors and that "communicating" the virtual is not a technological issue, but an epistemological question.

Categories and Subject Descriptors: J.5 [Arts and Humanities]; J.4 [SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES]; H.5 [INFORMATION INTERFACES AND PRESENTATION]

1. *Building Virtual Rome* Exhibition

The organisation of the exhibition *Building Virtual Rome*, was aimed at calling for a collective and global effort from diverse sectors that have already broached the subjects of ancient Rome and technology, discussing and examining the international projects, scientifically selecting the best examples from each sector, and offering to a general audience a chance to view and comment them. This international exhibition: "Building Virtual Rome" was the first world initiative dedicated to ancient Rome and its Empire, in terms of virtual archaeology.

1.1 Trajan's Markets, Rome

The exhibition took place inside an archaeological monument, Trajan's Markets, which is not only a place of extreme beauty and a highly suggestive setting for Italians and the millions of international tourists that Rome hosts, but it is also an archaeological site of international monumental and historical importance and value, which link past and future (figure 1).

1.2 - The Exhibition Itinerary and Sections

The exhibition itinerary was separated into four sections, based on different technological and cultural themes.

Figure 1. *Trajan's Markets: the exhibition place*

Section 1. The ancient city of Rome

This section offered applications related to the proto-historical, republican and imperial age of ancient Rome in its topographical, architectural and urban contexts.

Section 2. The Roman Empire

This section offered applications concerning the topography and Roman architecture in the rest of areas in the Roman Empire.

Section 3. Research and Experimentation

This section devoted to particularly innovative projects that are not necessarily linked to the theme of ancient Rome, but involve all the themes of virtual archaeology, interfaces, software development, advanced visualisation solutions, artificial intelligence, mobile systems, avatars, robotics, motion capture, and virtual sets - to name just a few.

Section 4. Special Guests

Different kind of technological solutions and applications were hosted, from the “traditional” computer-graphics movie, with no interaction at all for visitors, to complex VR applications which used common or high-tech devices (mouse, joystick, joy pad, haptic devices, etc.). (Figure 2)

Figure 2. The exhibition itinerary and types of tech solutions

1.3 Selection Criteria

Many research institutes, private companies, freelance professionals, public/private authorities and professional studios applied to the call for projects that was published over the web (www.buildingvirtualrome.org). The Scientific Committee used the following criteria to select the projects for the exhibition:

- Cultural content
- Innovation and experimental technology
- Graphic quality
- Congruity of treated themes
- Quality of didactics and communication
- Ability to create involvement in the narrative
- Interaction and edutainment
- Impact of knowledge and learning dynamics

More than 50 projects were selected and were displayed in

a “Cinema” room, as movies. For 14 of them an interactive installation was created in the small rooms which, during Roman times, had been shops of a big market (*tabernae*). Visitors could find outside each *taberna* an explanatory panel in Italian and English, while at the entrance they could have a short leaflet with general explanations about the exhibit, a short introduction of each installation and the suggestion of three different tours.

2. The VR installations

Table 1 shows a complete list of the interactive installations available. For further information the public web site is still available: <http://www.itabc.cnr.it/buildingvirtualrome/>.

NAME	TYPE OF APPLICATION	INTER-FACE	CONTENT
Gladiators	Audiovisual	Screen, 3d glasses	Gladiators fight at Colosseum
Virtual Roman Forum by Virginia Univ: B. Fricher	Audiovisual	Screen, Speakers	Pre-recorded movie of real-time navigation of reconstructed Roman forum
Trajan's Markets by Trajan's Markets Museum	Audiovisual	Screen, Speakers	Audiovisuals on different projects of the Markets
Cinema room	Multimedia	Screen, trackball	Movies on participating applications
Ancient Rome Tour by Altair4	Multimedia	Screen, Speakers, trackball	Spatio-temporal navigation of Rome with texts, images and VR reconstructions.
Complotum by TEAR	Multimedia	Screen, Speakers, trackball	Images, text audio explanations and VR reconstructions of the site
Appia Antica (figure 3) by CNR ITABC	Virtual Reality	Screen, Anaglyph glasses, Speakers, mouse, Joystick.	VR real time navigation inside the archaeological park of Appia Antica with avatars, audios, movies.
Diocletian's Baths Criptoportic by ACS	Virtual Reality- Audiovisual	Screen, Speakers, Mouse, numerical keyboard	VR navigation in the reconstructed city depicted on a wall in Diocletian's baths, with free navigation or pre-recorded visit.
E-Sparks (figure 4) By Plancton Art Studio	Artificial Intelligence	Screen, Speakers, camera and microph.	Artificial creatures living in underwater environment that learn and organize themselves through interaction with visitors.
Pure Forme Museum By PERCRO	Virtual Reality	Screen, Haptic device, passive stereo Glasses	Ancient statues inside a VR museum that can be “touched” through 3D visual - haptic devices
Theater of Pompej by King's Visualis. Lab	Multimedia, VR interactive environment	Screen, Mouse Numerical keyboard	VR reconstructions of Roman sites, and web based explanations ton them.
Mausoleum of	Multimedia	Screen,	Text, drawings and

NAME	TYPE OF APPLICATION	INTERFACE	CONTENT
Arrigo VII (figure 6) by CNR ISTI		Mouse	interactive 3D scanned images of VR statues in mausoleum of Arrigo VII (Pisa)
House of Centenario, Pompeii by CINECA	Virtual Reality	Screen, Joypad	VR navigation (free or automatic) in the House of Centenario; switching possibilities between nowadays and original state.
Multimedia Book (figure 5) by Fabricators	Virtual Reality	Screen, passive stereo Glasses, joystick	VR stereo navigation on an artistic reconstruction of Florence and its culture.
Cave Fruition - CNR ISSIA	Robots	Robots PC to guide them	Robots used for ancient cave investigation
Domus Aurea By La Sapienza	Multimedia	Monitor, mouse	Reconstruction of Roman Domus Aurea with information on it

Figure 3. Appia Park Narrative Museum (CNR ITABC)

Figure 4. E-Sparks (Plancton Art Studio)

3. The visitors survey: goals and methodology

Rome exhibit offered the great opportunity to undertake an evaluation about the use of ICT, which is becoming more and more a central issue in the Cultural Heritage dissemination field. The special conditions of this exhibition allowed us to concentrate in two different questions: first of all, the perception of ICT use as a communication tool by audiences (because although their utility might be evident to specialists, technology cannot be fully effective without integrating the addressees' points of view and needs); the second question concerned the use and usability of different interfaces.

To that end, and based on on current specific methodology [VHH05], [MCM88], [AP96], we planned four different

interviews and observations to be carried out at different moments of the visit. Due to non homogeneity of the applications, it was not easy to have homogeneous results.

Figure 5. Multimedia Book (Fabricators: F. Fishnaller)

Figure 6. Arrigo VII funerary monument (CNR ISTI)

1) **Initial interview.** At the entrance, a series of questions were asked to visitors. The goal was to analyse their expectations before the real visit and how they had known about the event, in order to understand also how public communication had worked.

2) **Final interview.** At the exit, after the visit, people were asked to answer other questions in order to gather their impressions and opinions about what they have seen. Some specific questions in the final interview were related with:

- the installation the visitor had enjoyed the most;
- the installation which had involved the most the visitor;
- the installation which had allowed more interaction;
- the installation which had allowed a better learning.

3) **Specific interview.** In each *taberna* some visitors were just observed silently in order to see their natural reaction to applications. Other were asked to answer to a short interview on the level of involvement, enjoyment they felt and of knowledge acquired in each *taberna*. Eventual

difficulties in the interaction/comprehension were also annotated.

4) **Time.** The last analysis was meant to calculate the average time a visitor was spending in each *taberna*, both passively and interacting with each application.

4. Some preliminary results

At the end of the exhibition we saw that Saturday and Sunday were most busy days. The average visitor was a man (60% men and 40% women), adult between 20 and 35 years old, mainly teacher or office worker. He was coming from the place where the exhibition took place, in this case Rome, and he was visiting it with his family. He had also some knowledge about archaeology and also, perhaps a bit more, about computers, which he used both at home and for work. Interviewed visitors declared to visit museums or exhibitions fairly often, and as much as 65% of them (all categories of age and both genders, regardless of the previous knowledge about Archaeology) expected to obtain an intellectual benefit from them. The second category of visitors were young people, mainly students, and finally retired people. In terms of general results, the most appreciated *tabernae* were "Ancient Rome tour", "Appia Antica Park" and "Pure Form Museum"; secondly, "E-sparks" was appreciated for enjoyment. The main means of publicity for the exhibition were newspapers and the posters distributed in the city. Only three persons found it out in the Internet.

4.1 Expectations and attitudes towards the use of ICT in Cultural Heritage field

Technology in the CH field is an attraction for people, a good reason to visit an exhibition and particularly to visit the present one. They didn't see it as an aim by itself but as a means of communication, an intellectual benefit needed for a cultural visit; therefore it should not influence the price of the ticket.

When asked about the goals of technology in the cultural field, visitors answered technology should be used in CH field to improve its internal activities (research and preservation) as well as dissemination, and the option was directly related with a highest or lowest knowledge of Archaeology. In any case, technology was seen as a tool that can change practices in the whole field, it is a total flexible tool. Concerning ICT utility for exhibitions, 50% of the interviewed people considered that they are meant for the improvement of dissemination, understanding and learning. In this case, audiences thought multimedia are better than text or images to present Cultural Heritage and requested from ICT applications richness of information and clarity. In other words, they gave them a learning or communicative purpose, far beyond pure entertainment. Finally, the most disseminated concept of "Virtual Archaeology" combined the goals of Archaeology and some of the properties of Virtual Reality: it was mainly associated with the reconstruction or depiction of the past and not with scientific research or the idea of intangible

heritage, which has been introduced in the field. However, all visitors were sure virtual reality cannot substitute real experience or real visit of a site.

4.2 Use of interfaces and opinions about the exhibition

We considered that the main factors involved in applied digital technologies were enjoyment, immersion, interaction and engagement. From the answers to the "open" questions we deduced that enjoyment was related to novelty and sense of presence. On the other hand, if it was easy and interactive it was appreciated by children but not by adults, who found it funny but useless in the context of a Cultural Heritage settlement.

Elements determining immersion were novelty and richness of information, as well as graphic realism. This means that immersion was understood both as engagement and as a real sensation of presence or, in other words, a combination of physical, emotional and intellectual factors. Interaction was associated with the system's visible capacity of response, but also the quantity of information was appreciated. This indicates that interactivity is not only physical but also demands an active participation of the user, both physical and cognitive.

Concerning engagement, the main involved factors in positive as well as negative perceptions were: the capacity of exploration or comprehension of the contents, which was totally determinant; the graphic realism (specially in passive applications); and the usability of the interface, for the understanding of which they preferred the help of a human guide and which was critical for the success and the user satisfaction.

These preliminary data showed that just counting the time spent with an exhibit cannot be a good indicator of its effectiveness because many different elements, positive and negative, influence this measure: type of exhibit (audiovisual, VR application or Multimedia), real use of the device, presence of other visitors and problems with the interface [Puj06].

4.3 Learning and understanding of contents

A way to see what people had understood/learned in the exhibits is to ask about its goal. The answers showed that visitors were retaining more the application than the details of the contents and in general, could not tell if or how technology helped them to better understand the contents. Taking into account that the aim of the exhibition was not to foster learning about Ancient Rome but to show different technological solutions related to that topic, we can affirm that it was fulfilled. However, this also demonstrates that if technology has to serve as a learning tool it should be really "invisible", that is, intuitive both from the point of view of the navigation inside the virtual environment (show clearly all the possibilities in the screen) and of the interface operation (only one input device or if possible none at all –use the body as an interface-, put instructions integrated inside the application, etc.), in order not to interfere with the learning of contents. These preliminary results also demonstrated that VR can

activate a correspondence with iconic skills or mental representations but still some expectations of people are mainly focused on verbal learning and virtual storytelling. Factors involved in learning were the richness of information but also the quality of the reconstructions, specially if they can be related to previous knowledge or experiences. Realism, which is still one of the major concerns for designers, proved to be not decisive for ICT applications' effectiveness from a strictly cognitive point of view. We have to be aware of the fact that there is an ontological gap between the virtual and the real world that technology will never be able to transcend. This is why total realism should not be a goal, but instead Virtual Reality applications should accomplish an epistemological function –in most of the cases better achievable through non-photorealistic rendering– because this is what audiences expect from them [Puj06].

5. Conclusion

In a first preliminary study, it is very difficult to have definitive answers in the field of interaction/relations between virtual environments, virtual content, museums and final users/visitors. In particular we noticed that a wide percentage of projects and applications of virtual heritage are never experimented and monitored with people, but they born and die in digital labs. In fact, in many cases the evaluation of the systems is done by digital content and metaphors and not by the direct users' interaction and behaviours. On the contrary, interaction and feedback determine the virtual embodiment, the empathy factor really crucial for learning and communication. The more the user is immersed in a network of information, the more he/she will be able to have a experience and a knowledge to communicate.

Hence, it is quite obvious that we need more data and information about the sustainability of advanced virtual technologies (VR, multimedia, haptics, computer graphics) in relation with the human factor and dynamic interaction. In the case of the exhibition "Building Virtual Rome", about 90% of the installations of virtual archaeology were presented for the first time to a public audience.

As preliminary conclusions, according to the survey and to the analyses of the virtual projects in relation with the visitors' feedback, it is possible to list the following key points:

- the number of visitors of museums or cultural exhibitions can be *strongly* increased by the use of installations and devices of advanced digital technologies;
- the use of VR systems, in particular, augments the expectations about the exhibition;
- in the case of the Museum of Trajan's Market the number of visitors was increased ten times during the exhibition in comparison with the rest of the year;
- this effect of attraction depends on the curiosity towards the digital technologies and mainly towards virtual environments;

- the feedback of the public is different according to the skills, the age and the interest towards the applications;
- cultural content, software and devices have to be integrated in an interaction system (???) to be successful;
- direct interaction with virtual environments is crucial for the users, but typically they require instructions and training (a difficult approach creates a lack in expectation and a disappointment);
- the "embodiment" factor depends on the quality of interaction and connectivity in the informative space of VR systems;
- virtual contents based on spatial information are able to a better help for dynamic behaviours and users' navigation;
- the example of "Appia Antica" VR application shows that the combination of virtual storytelling with the landscape reconstruction creates a strong "embodiment" between users and a high degree of digital memorization;
- haptics and robotics ("tangible virtual") are appreciated and used by the public, even if the interfaces are not so natural and the behaviours are quite limited.
- Experts or people working in CH field are probably still thinking that Virtual Reality could "threaten" cultural objects, preventing visitors to go, after a virtual visit, to see the real site. In fact no visitor seems to think that virtual can substitute real experiences.

Finally, from this first analyses we can say that virtual heritage applications need to have a more integrated approach between cultural contents, interfaces and technological devices. Interdisciplinary teams need to be created since if an application is developed (and often tends to remain) in a research lab, communication tends to be forgotten. Too many projects are focussed only to enhance a part of the system (for example the digital interface or the computer graphic models) and not to have a holistic vision of the information. Perception, capacity of learning, psychology, emotions, empathy, 3D behaviours, connectivity, dynamic processes of learning, embodiment, are fundamental factors of the virtual communication. Unfortunately, we don't have a deep understanding of the impact and the relationships of advanced digital technologies with the human factor, so the Virtual Museum, or the Virtual Musealization are still a "chimera", at least in epistemological terms.

Agreements

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References

[AP96] ASENSIO M., POL MÉNDEZ E.: Cuando la mente va al museo: un enfoque cognitivo-receptivo de los estudios de público. *IX Jornadas estatales DEAC-Museos: La exposición* (1996), 83-133

[EP06] ECONOMOU M., PUJOL L., Educational tool or expensive toy? Evaluating VR evaluation and its relevance for Virtual Heritage. In *New Heritage: beyond verosimilitude. Conference on Cultural Heritage and New Media. Proceedings of the New Heritage Conference, Hong Kong, 13th-14th March 2006*. Kvan T., Kalay Y, The Faculty of Architecture, University of Hong-Kong:284-302

[Puj06] LAIA PUJOL TOST, PhD dissertation "Aproximació semiòtica a l'ús de la Realitat Virtual per la difusió de l'Arqueologia als museus", tesi doctoral dirigida para la Dra. Paloma Gonzalez Maracen, Dept. of Prehistory, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2006

[McM88] MCMANUS P. M.: Good companions ... more on the social determination of learning-related behaviour in a science museum. *International Journal of Museum Management and Curatorship* (1988) 7, 37-44.

[Rou05] ROUSSOU M., Can interactivity in virtual environments enable conceptual learning? In *7th Virtual Reality International Conference*. Laval, France. 57-64

[VHH05] VOM LEHN D., HEATH C., HINDMARSH J.: Rethinking interactivity: design for participation in museums and galleries. *Re-thinking Technology in Museums: Towards a New Understanding of People's Experience in Museums* (2005), www.idc.ul.ie/museumworkshop/programme.html.